

in this issue >>>

- Why are pet euthanasia statistics so high?
- Is RSPCA Australia concerned about abandoned animals' welfare?
- Why you should adopt an animal, not shop?

An Insight into the pet welfare and ethical adoption

Adopt a pet

Why is it ethical?

current topic >>>

Don't shop- Adopt!

According to RSPCA, they provide shelters for animals needing a home. Choosing to adopt will give the animal second chance at life and support the animal welfare, you will also gain best friend in your life. RSPCA Australia (2025).

RSPCA and abandoned animals

Animals in need of new home or else!

Dear person interested in animal welfare, you are responsible for your decisions about what you will do, to help an animal in need or thinking about getting a new pet.

This article might persuade you to be aware and think carefully about what is currently happening with abandoned cats and dogs who have been relinquished to RSPCA shelters across Australia.

RSPCA Australia (2024) is a charity organisation. They are reliant on charity donations and funding.

Every bit of donations or animal adoptions helps. The shelters are still accepting abandoned and rescued animals, but do they need help in certain areas.? What needs to be explored and highlighted to ensure there is best possible outcome for the animal, RSPCA shelter and future and current pet owner?

RSPCA shelters are doing their best to bring awareness to adoption options (RSPCA Australia, 2025) and programs. But do all Australian states have the same support in their individual locations?

17,468

**Dogs and
26,704**

Cats

were relinquished to

RSPCA shelters in

2023/2024

How can cat and dog euthanasia be reduced, and do all Australian RSPCA shelters have same support and programs to avoid this last resort decision?

What are reasons for euthanasia? Can the outcomes be improved with better adoption programs?

How can you help, dear reader? To start we need to be educated about current numbers of animal outcomes in past financial year. Pinpoint the problem areas and hopefully be persuasive to drive pet adoption and influence decision to help shelters that are struggling.

Did you know?

Sources: (Todorovic, 2025), (RSPCA Australia, 2024)

2842 dogs were euthanised in Australia last year.

5148 cats were euthanised in Australia last year.

Reasons for dog and cat euthanasia? >>>

Reasons for euthanasia - dogs per state

Reasons for euthanasia- cats per state

Dogs outcomes and change from last year
Data Source: (Todorovic, 2025)

WA, VIC, TAS, SA, QLD, NT, NSW and ACT by Total: and States:

● WA ● VIC ● TAS ● SA ● QLD ● NT ● NSW ● ACT

Above stacked column chart data shows that there was slight change to last year's outcomes of dogs in shelters. The pie chart below shows that majority of cat intake was rehomed. Indicating improvement and allowing for insight that greater awareness and education could drive change.

Sum of Data: by Cats

Queensland and NSW have the largest statistics and programs for rehoming. Other states have less data or no data. The potential reasons can be lack of record keeping, lack of resources or smaller volume of sheltered animals.

The volume of cats and dogs in shelters is astounding.

It clearly is an issue across all Australian states. RSPCA and other animal welfare organizations and charities seek better awareness to responsible pet ownership and conditions of animals in care and during outcome decisions. RSPCA NSW (2025)

Tables below show last year's situation in RSPCA shelters. Whether states keep accurate records, or there is less volume of shelter intake, it is still alarming. (Todorovic, 2025) (RSPCA Australia, 2024)

According to RSPCA NSW (2025) the issue can be improved with microchipping and desexing support, awareness of cruelty reporting, adopting shelter animals, not breeding irresponsibly and other means.

Ultimately, it's up to you, decision maker.

If you need a new pet- adopt!

If you concerned about animal welfare- spread awareness!

If you make decisions in Australian animal shelters- ensure you have support from your governing bodies!

References:

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